

Rare Earth Doped Thin Films for Optical Quantum Technologies

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Abstract

Rare earth doped crystals show, at low temperatures, extremely narrow optical homogeneous linewidths, as well as long spin coherence lifetimes, a unique combination in the solid state. This makes these materials attractive for optical quantum technologies like quantum communication and processing. Most of the results in this field have so far used bulk crystals because of their exceptional spectroscopic properties. Crystalline thin films could combine these properties with the possibilities offered by integration in photonic circuits in terms of compactness, stability, energy efficiency, and scalability.

In this review, we summarize recent results on different platforms containing rare earth ions and targeting quantum technologies, including lithium niobate and silicon films, and oxide films deposited on Si. Current approaches for obtaining thin films and devices are described, together with RE spectroscopic properties and applications to quantum technologies. The opportunities and challenges offered or faced by the different platforms are also discussed.

KEYWORDS

rare earth, thin films, quantum technologies, integrated photonics

1 | INTRODUCTION

Rare earth (RE) doped crystals have unique optical properties in the solid state and have been investigated by high-resolution and coherent spectroscopy for about 50 years¹. Because of the shielding of the 4f electrons by the closed 5s and 5p shells and the associated decrease in sensitivity to their environment, RE can exhibit very narrow lines at temperatures below ≈ 4 K from the infrared to the UV range. Indeed, the individual ion linewidth, called the homogeneous linewidth Γ_h , can be found well below the kHz range in several RE-crystal systems, whereas the envelope of these lines, which is the inhomogeneous linewidth Γ_{inh} , is typically on the order of a few GHz or less^{1,2,3}. The narrowest optical transition in a solid has been reported for Er^{3+} ions doped in a high-quality yttrium orthosilicate single crystal at low temperature and under a strong magnetic field. It amounts to $\Gamma_h = 73$ Hz⁴!

These properties make RE ions promising for quantum technologies (QT). The narrow transitions translate into long-lived optical quantum states as their lifetime, or coherence lifetime T_2 , is related to Γ_h by $\Gamma_h = 1/\pi T_2$. Moreover, RE ions have electron or nuclear spins that can show very long T_2 up to several hours for $\text{Eu}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{SiO}_5$ nuclear spins⁵ and 10s of ms for $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{CaWO}_4$ electron spins⁶. This makes them ideal

for quantum information storage and processing, while the optical transitions provide a quantum interface to light and the possibility of optical control of the spin states^{3,7}.

This has triggered a strong interest in applications of RE-doped crystals to quantum communication and computing. Notably, coherent and quantum storage has been demonstrated in a variety of systems with long storage time, high bandwidth, and high efficiency^{8,9,10,11}, leading to demonstrations of entanglement between light and a crystal^{12,13} as well as between remote crystals¹⁴. These experiments, and others dealing with quantum gates^{15,16}, were performed using large ensembles of ions embedded in bulk crystals. In some cases, light-RE interaction was increased using waveguides, typically with a transverse mode size of several microns, obtained by laser-writing^{17,18} or ion diffusion¹⁹. Following studies in other solid-state systems, such as quantum dots and color centers in diamond⁷, it appeared that using single RE ions could open new possibilities. For example, by removing the inhomogeneities in transition frequencies and interaction strengths, scalable schemes for quantum processing could be envisioned²⁰ as well as quantum networks based on single spin-single photon entanglement. However, RE ions are very dim emitters - a consequence of the 4f electron shielding - and efficient single ion detection requires coupling them to resonators, providing strong Purcell enhancement. This has been achieved using

resonators milled in²¹ or placed on top of bulk crystals^{22,23}. Alternatively, nanoparticles²⁴ or membranes obtained from bulk crystals²⁵ can be placed in open fiber micro-cavities. In some of these systems, single shot RE spin readout has been demonstrated^{26,27}, as well as coupling between a single RE to a nuclear spin register²⁸ or emission of indistinguishable photons at the telecom wavelength²⁹.

These results are closely connected to the spectacular development of classical and quantum integrated photonics^{30,31,32,33}. Platforms have been developed in different wavelength ranges to implement low-loss waveguides, switches, filters, or beam splitters and complement them with photon sources and detectors. RE ions can provide additional functionalities, including telecom wavelength sources with spin-photon entanglement, quantum processing, quantum memories, or microwave-to-optical transduction.

In this review, we focus on RE-doped thin films that we loosely define as layers with thickness ranging from 10s of nm to sub-micron. This approach is expected to bring several benefits compared to those mentioned above. First, such thin films enable RE-light coupling in waveguides or resonators showing low losses and strong confinement. Second, these structures can be fabricated in the films themselves or in other materials, which then takes advantage of near-field coupling between light and RE (**Figure 1**). The thin films can be made out of bulk crystals, like lithium niobate or silicon, that support the fabrication of high-quality photonic structures showing functionalities such as beam splitters, interferometers, or optical switches. These possibilities can be further extended by films grown by bottom-up methods on undoped multi-purpose substrates, like Si, that can be obtained with very high quality, large sizes, at a low price, and on which high-performance photonic structures can be fabricated. In addition, grown thin films require a low amount of raw materials and can be structured layer by layer, on the nanoscale, to optimize properties.

Fulfilling RE-doped thin films promises for quantum applications is however challenging as it requires obtaining suitable structures in which RE optical and spin properties are preserved. In this respect, a key point is to achieve long optical and spin coherence lifetimes despite RE ions experiencing noise related to nearby interfaces, to defects and impurities introduced during synthesis, or to the hosts themselves. If these can be overcome, RE-doped thin films will offer efficient integration with other necessary optical functionalities, extreme compactness, increased stability with respect to experimental conditions, scalability, and lower energy consumption.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes RE-doped thin film and device growth or fabrication. Section 3 focuses on the optical and spin spectroscopy of RE ions in different crystalline hosts and discusses the challenges to preserve their properties in thin films. Finally, Section 4 presents results advancing toward applications of thin films to quantum memories, single-ion-based devices, and hybrid systems.

FIGURE 1 Photonic devices based on rare earth doped thin films.

(a) Top: cross-section of a waveguide fabricated in a thin film (yellow) doped with RE ions (green points) and bonded to a low-index material (blue). Light propagates into the RE doped thin film. Bottom: Example of the above structure with a waveguide and a ring resonator fabricated in an Er^{3+} doped LiNbO_3 on insulator (SiO_2) thin film (SEM image). Adapted with permission.³⁴ ©2022, American Physical Society. (b) Top: cross-section of a device fabricated in a RE doped thin film (yellow) grown on top of a guiding material (gray) that is bonded to a low-index material (blue). Light propagates in the guiding material, and evanescently couples to RE ions. Bottom: Example with waveguides and photonic crystal cavities made from an Er^{3+} doped TiO_2 thin film deposited on a Si film bonded to SiO_2 (SEM image). Adapted with permission.³⁵©2023, Optica Publishing Group.

2 | THIN FILMS GROWTH AND DEVICE FABRICATION

2.1 | Bottom-up growth techniques

RE-doped thin films grown for QT have been mainly obtained using molecular beam epitaxy (MBE), chemical vapor deposition (CVD), and atomic layer deposition (ALD). They are well-established processes for obtaining films with thicknesses between tens and hundreds of nm,^{40,41} which is well suited for coupling the embedded RE ions to photonic or electronic structures (see **Figure 1** and Section 2.3).

Most of the works described in the following sections have focused on oxide films deposited on silicon substrates or made of silicon itself. Besides spectroscopic considerations (see Sec. 3), this is first because Si is a highly mature platform for integrated photonic circuits³¹ in which many components are available, such as low-loss waveguides, resonators with high-quality factors, interferometers, and filters. Second, oxide films on silicon are used extensively in complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) technology and are, therefore, compatible with large-scale, high-throughput industrial processes. It should be noted that the Si bandgap of about 1.1 eV or 8800 cm^{-1} restricts its

FIGURE 2 Rare earth doped thin films grown by bottom-up methods. (a) Scheme of a CVD reactor. Precursors in the form of metal complexes in a solvent are injected and evaporated in chambers. They are then carried under low pressure by a flow of Ar and O₂ to a heated tubular furnace where thin films grow on e.g. silicon wafers. Adapted with permission.³⁶ ©2020, AIP Publishing. (b) Left: surface of a CVD polycrystalline film of Y₂O₃ deposited on Si (001). Right: XRD pattern showing a strong texture along [111] of the Y₂O₃ film. Adapted with permission.³⁶ ©2020, AIP Publishing. (c) TOF-SIMS analysis of Y₂O₃ films deposited on Si by CVD at 650 °C. The as-grown film (left) shows sharp interfaces between the Si substrate, a thermally grown SiO₂ layer, and the deposited Y₂O₃ film. After annealing at 1200 °C, a substantial diffusion of oxygen and silicon results in a thick mixed silicate phase. Adapted under the terms of the CC-BY license.³⁷ ©2022, N. Harada et al. (d) TEM image and diffraction patterns (inset) of an epitaxial (111) CeO₂ thin film deposited on (111) Si by MBE. Interfacial oxidation during the film growth leads to amorphous silicate layers. Adapted under the terms of the CC-BY license.³⁸ ©2024, G. Grant et al. (e) TiO₂ thin films deposited by MBE on SrTiO₃ and Si. TEM images reveal epitaxial and polycrystalline structures, respectively. Adapted under the terms of the CC-BY license.³⁹ ©2024, M. Singh et al.

transparency range to the infrared, which is, however, accessible to the 1.5 μm telecom range emission of Er³⁺ ions. In addition to Si, other substrates have been considered, like SrTiO₃³⁹, LaAlO₃⁴² or YSZ⁴³, mainly to provide a lattice match to the deposited films and achieve epitaxial growth.

CVD is a technique in which precursors, such as metal complexes, are mixed with a gas and react on the surface of a heated substrate to form a crystalline film (Figure 2a). CVD can reach high growth rates, on the order of 100s of nm/h, and can ensure good oxygen stoichiometry for oxide films because it uses a relatively high O₂ pressure. On Si substrates, films like those made of Y₂O₃ are typically polycrystalline with a strong texture (Figure 2b,c)³⁶. CVD can also be used to grow epitaxial Si films on Si substrates starting from highly purified gases such as silane (SiH₄)⁴⁴. ALD is similar to CVD but uses a step-by-step process in which monoatomic layers are deposited and then oxidized. This enables very accurate deposition, especially for nm thick films. To ensure monolayer

coverage of the surface, ALD uses substrate temperatures of typically 100-300 °C and is therefore prone to grow amorphous films. Full crystallization, which is required for narrow RE linewidths, can be obtained through post-annealing^{45,1}.

MBE operates in ultra-high vacuum and typically uses pure elements, such as metals, as precursors⁴⁶. It can, therefore, be used to grow films with very high purity. The very low O₂ pressure used in MBE is also favorable to epitaxial growth of oxide films on silicon substrates avoiding the formation of an initial amorphous SiO₂ layer on its surface (Figure 2d,e). This, however, requires a proper lattice match which can be obtained for example with Y₂O₃⁴⁶ or CeO₂³⁸ (respective mismatches of -2.4% and -0.4%). These hosts can be moreover readily doped with RE ions. Pulsed laser deposition (PLD)⁴⁷, electron beam evaporation⁴⁸, and ionized cluster beam deposition⁴⁹ are other growth methods that can achieve epitaxial growth of Y₂O₃ on Si.

FIGURE 3 Rare earth doped thin films fabricated by top-down techniques. Fabrication process of LNOI thin films by implantation, bonding, thermally induced splitting, and final polishing. Adapted with permission.³⁴ ©2022, American Physical Society.

Thin film structures are typically assessed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) for phase identification, texture, grain size, and epitaxial film mosaicity. Morphology and smoothness can be observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) or atomic force microscopy (AFM). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and secondary ion mass spectroscopy (SIMS) can provide valuable information on the substrate-film interface like epitaxial relations, presence of amorphous layers, or element diffusion (Figure 2c,d,e).

Thin films can be treated after growth, and studies on Y₂O₃ nanoparticles, for example, have shown a dramatic improvement in RE homogeneous linewidths after high-temperature annealing or oxygen plasma processing that cured part of the defects present in the particles⁵⁰. However, as for the deposition process, high-temperature annealing of thin films grown on substrates with different expansion coefficients may lead to large strain in the film. Strain is released by the creation of extended structural defects or even the appearance of cracks that can affect RE ion linewidths. Annealing can also lead to the diffusion of chemical species at the substrate-film interface or within the films, potentially dramatically changing the RE ion environment (Figure 2c). This effect can be mitigated by techniques such as rapid thermal annealing (RTA)³⁷.

2.2 | Top-down Thin Film Fabrication

Thin films can be obtained from single crystals of e.g. Si or LiNbO₃ by techniques where ion beam implantation of a species such as H⁺ or He⁺ creates a damaged layer at a depth of a few 100s of nm (Figure 3)^{51,52}. A crystal membrane can then be mechanically exfoliated or thermally split, bonded to a Si substrate with a top SiO₂ layer created by oxidation, and finally polished. The final structure is referred to as SOI (silicon on insulator) or LNOI (lithium niobate on insulator). RE can be introduced

into these films by implantation^{44,53} or by fabricating the film from a doped bulk crystal^{54,34}. In the case of implantation, post-annealing is necessary to repair structural damage caused by the heavy RE ions with high energy and recover RE properties^{55,56}.

2.3 | Device Fabrication

RE-doped thin films offer a strong potential for creating scalable photonic circuits containing high-quality emitters. These circuits can be created in SOI films using procedures developed for integrated photonics that combine lithography and etching techniques³¹. RE ions can be doped in-situ or implanted in silicon, which is a more scalable approach⁵⁷. Implantation can take place before or after the fabrication of photonic structures. In the first case, the structures are not damaged but, unless masking is used, RE ions are present in the whole chip, which can result in unwanted background signals⁵⁸. In the second case, the process is more scalable and, with masking, enables localization of the RE ions. However, it requires post-annealing to improve not only the RE properties but also those of the photonic structures.

LNOI is also a well-developed platform for photonics in which low-losses structures, like waveguides and resonators, can be achieved³². It is also a non-linear crystal whose refractive index can be electrically tuned, a feature allowing, for example, fast control of resonators' central frequency with respect to that of the RE ions⁵⁹. Photonic structures can be patterned into doped LNOI films, which may lead to better RE properties at the expense of having dopants also outside the desired locations³⁴. Alternatively, as in the case of SOI, implantation before or after structuration is possible, offering greater scalability and dopant localization, but requiring careful post-annealing to cure damages⁵⁶.

RE in oxide films deposited on SOI can also be coupled to structures patterned into the Si film. This requires etching through both the oxide and Si films, which was achieved with a 22 nm thick polycrystalline TiO₂ film on a 220 nm thick Si one⁶⁰.

It is also possible to assemble films on photonic structures by e.g. direct Van der Waals contact, which enables using a broader range of materials, including SiN, which has a wider transparency window.^{61,62} Open fiber cavities could also be used with thin films containing RE to obtain enhanced light coupling with RE ions, with the advantage of fast tuning of the cavity's resonance^{63,24,64}.

3 | RARE EARTH SPECTROSCOPY

In this section, we review spectroscopic results obtained on ensembles of RE ions in thin films. Experiments involving single ions are discussed in Sec. 4.2. We moreover focus on the optical properties that are the most relevant for and specific to QT, namely inhomogeneous and homogeneous linewidths. Indeed, for most works reported below, photo-luminescence (PL) spectra, usually recorded at medium resolution, and PL decay times are very close to those obtained in bulk crystals

and will not be discussed in depth. At the end of the section, we present a short summary of RE spin properties in thin films.

3.1 | Inhomogeneous and Homogeneous Optical Linewidths

Inhomogeneous linewidths (Figures 4a and 5a) are generally measured by recording photo-luminescence excitation (PLE) spectra because the small number of emitters in thin films gives low absorption. Transitions of interest have small homogeneous broadening at temperatures below ≈ 4 K, and generally involve the lowest crystal field levels of transitions between the ground multiplet and an excited multiplet well-separated from the next lower ones³. This avoids fast non-radiative relaxation between levels that would considerably broaden the lines. To reach high resolution, transitions can be scanned by tunable single-frequency lasers, often using pulsed schemes to separate spontaneous emission and laser excitation. This is facilitated by the long excited population lifetimes (T_1), usually in the 100s of μs to several ms, for most RE ions. Inhomogeneous broadening reflects the varying environments between RE ions in the probed volume and is generally caused by micro-strain induced by point and extended defects^{1,65}. Above a concentration of a few 100s of ppm and in high-quality crystals with low defect concentration, RE ions themselves may significantly contribute to Γ_{inh} ^{66,67}. Narrow inhomogeneous linewidths are an indication of high crystalline quality and thus correlate to some extent to narrow homogeneous linewidths. They are also useful to reach higher peak absorption for quantum memories, increase coupling in microwave-to-optical transducers, and finding single ions more easily at low doping concentrations.

As mentioned in the introduction, the homogeneous broadening Γ_h (Figure 4a) is a key parameter as it is inversely proportional to the quantum state lifetime T_2 . It can be measured by different techniques, the most common ones being photon echoes (PE), spectral hole burning (SHB), and saturation spectroscopy. Analogous to spin echoes, PE are collective spontaneous emissions that are created by two laser pulses that coherently excite and rephase an inhomogeneously broadened ensemble of emitters⁶⁸ (Figures 4b and 5b). The decay of the echo intensity as a function of the delay between the pulses gives access to the probed transition's T_2 and thus Γ_h . The technique can be extended to single ions by converting coherence into population by a third pulse and monitoring the resulting fluorescence. In contrast with ensemble measurements, a laser with sufficient phase coherence is required in this case²⁶.

SHB and saturation spectroscopy (also known as transient spectral hole burning, TSHB) are often used to investigate thin films because they can give stronger signals than PE for small numbers of emitters. Persistent SHB (Figures 4c and 5c) consists of transferring ground state population in resonance with a narrow laser to off-resonant shelving states, often long-lived electronic or spin levels^{68,3}. The resulting decrease in absorption at the laser frequency can be recorded as a spectral 'hole' in a PLE spectrum³⁶. The transition homogeneous linewidth, on

FIGURE 4 Optical spectroscopy of rare earth doped thin films. (a) Structure of RE transitions of interest at low temperature. The homogeneous linewidth Γ_h is typically several orders of magnitude narrower than the inhomogeneous linewidth Γ_{inh} . (b) Left: photon echo sequence. Two laser pulses separated by a delay τ respectively create and rephase optical coherence in an ensemble of ions, leading to a photon echo at time 2τ . Right: Γ_h can be determined by analysing the photon echo intensity decay I_{echo} as a function of 2τ , for example using $I_{\text{echo}} = I_0 \exp(-2(2\tau)/T_2)$. (c) Spectral hole burning (SHB). Left: a first pulse at frequency ν_{pump} transfers population of a RE sub-ensemble to shelving states. A second pulse at ν_{probe} , sent after the excited state population has decayed, measures absorption through fluorescence intensity. Right: repeating the sequence while varying ν_{probe} reconstructs the SHB spectrum. The hole width Γ_{hole} includes the laser linewidth and thus gives an upper limit on $2\Gamma_h$. (d) Saturation or transient hole burning spectroscopy. Left: a pulse containing several equally spaced spectral peaks excites an ensemble of ions which fluorescence intensity I_{fluo} is detected. Right: the sequence is repeated for varying $\delta\nu$ and at different laser powers, which leads to an upper limit for Γ_h .

the time scale of the SHB sequence (Figure 4c), is then related to the hole linewidth by $\Gamma_h = \Gamma_{\text{hole}}/2 - \Gamma_L$, where Γ_L is the laser linewidth. More

details on SHB can be found in Ref.⁶⁹. Saturation spectroscopy (Figures 4d and 5d) is a similar technique, which gives access to Γ_h on the time scale of the excited state lifetime T_1 . It is also useful in the absence of long-lived shelving states^{70,44}. A laser excitation is first spectrally shaped into a comb of several equally spaced frequencies with enough intensity in each peak to reach the saturation regime. When the peaks' detuning $\delta\nu$ is much larger than Γ_h , the total PL intensity varies as a function of the laser intensity I as $N\sqrt{I}$ since each peak excites independent sub-ensembles of ions. This process burns separate power-broadened holes by storing population in the excited state. In the opposite case, i.e. $\delta\nu \ll \Gamma_h$, the peaks excite the same ions, burn a single hole, and the PL decreases as it is now proportional to \sqrt{NI} . Recording the PL intensity as a function of the comb frequency separation and laser power thus enables determining Γ_h ⁴⁴. It should be noted that this method requires careful consideration when low laser power is used, as it may lead to underestimated homogeneous linewidth values⁷¹.

In contrast to PE, which can determine Γ_h on short time scales, SHB and saturation spectroscopy give Γ_h on a time scale of the order of the excited state T_1 , or on longer ones if shelving states are involved, and may thus include some additional broadening due to spectral diffusion, i.e. frequency wandering due to perturbations acting on times longer than the transition T_2 . The spectral diffusion linewidth⁷², Γ_{SD} , is an important parameter when spectral tailoring by optical pumping is required, like in quantum memory protocols (see Section 4.1).

Homogeneous broadening is caused by time-dependent fluctuations in the RE environment and includes interactions with phonons, two-level systems (TLS), and electric and magnetic fields³. The excited state lifetime (T_1) contribution is usually negligible¹. Studies on nanoparticles and ions close to the surface of bulk crystals suggest that Γ_h values in these cases are dominated by electric noise and/or TLS^{50,29}. Electric noise is likely due to surface charges, dangling bonds, or charged vacancies. TLS are related to residual disorder and has also been observed in micro-structured ceramics and even bulk crystals^{73,74,75}. Paramagnetic ions such as Er^{3+} are also sensitive to magnetic noise from fluctuating electron and nuclear spins, which makes oxide crystals preferable over e.g. fluorides because of the large nuclear magnetic moment of the 100% abundant ^{19}F spin. Magnetic noise can originate from the RE spins themselves, host nuclear spins, like ^{89}Y , or spins carried by impurities or other defects such as charged vacancies^{72,73,76}. Static superhyperfine interactions can also broaden optical lines by tens of kHz at low magnetic fields, as in the case of $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{SiO}_5$ ⁷⁷.

The next sections discuss results obtained in oxide thin films deposited on Si and other substrates, in implanted SOI films made by different techniques, and in doped and implanted LNOI films. Values for Γ_{inh} and Γ_h are reported in Table 1 for a number of systems, together with other structural and spectroscopic parameters. A summary of the limiting factors for optical properties in the different platforms and possible mitigations are shown in Table 2 and detailed below.

3.2 | Optical Properties of Rare Earth Doped in Grown Oxide Thin Films

Y_2O_3 thin films have been investigated using different growth methods and dopants. The motivation behind this choice is, on the one hand, the good structural properties that can be obtained, including epitaxial and textured films, and on the other hand, the excellent optical properties observed in bulk materials^{78,87,88,73,89,90,91}. It is important however to note that these properties can vary a lot depending on the synthesis methods and conditions, pointing to the difficulty in controlling defects, such as oxygen vacancies, in this matrix^{74,73}.

A first series of works investigated Eu^{3+} doped Y_2O_3 films. Reference values for bulk materials are among the best reported for RE ions: Γ_h can be as low as 760 Hz in bulk crystals and 3.2 kHz in transparent ceramics, with Γ_{inh} on the order of 10 to 20 GHz at 2% doping⁷⁸. Moreover, $\text{Eu}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles are the only ones so far that can exhibit homogeneous linewidths as low as 56 kHz for 100 nm size⁵⁰.

An early work reported properties of 2% $\text{Eu}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ in the cubic phase grown by metal-organic CVD on sapphire⁷⁹. The films were polycrystalline and 3 μm thick. At a temperature of 1.4 K, $\Gamma_{inh} = 90$ GHz and $\Gamma_h = 12$ MHz were measured by SHB for the ${}^7\text{F}_0 \rightarrow {}^5\text{D}_0$ transition at 581 nm. A linear increase of Γ_h with temperature, typical of TLS broadening, was observed with a slope of ≈ 1 MHz/K.

More recently, 5% Eu^{3+} doped Y_2O_3 films, with a polycrystalline structure and a 100 nm thickness, were grown on silicon substrates by ALD at around 300 °C⁴⁵. In this case, high-temperature post-annealing was necessary to improve Eu^{3+} PL intensity and decays, as well as to observe narrower transitions. Above 950 °C however, parasitic lines appeared because of silicon oxidation and the formation of silicate phases at the substrate/film interface. After process optimization (e.g. changes in deposition temperature, gas pulse and purge durations), high-resolution spectroscopy revealed the presence of a parasitic and poorly crystallized monoclinic Y_2O_3 phase. The ${}^7\text{F}_0 \rightarrow {}^5\text{D}_0$ transition inhomogeneous linewidth was about 200 MHz in the 800-950 °C annealing temperature range. As mentioned in Sec. 1, this broadening is likely to be due to the strain and subsequent defects created by the difference in thermal expansion coefficients between Si and Y_2O_3 (2.5×10^{-6} and $8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ respectively).

Direct liquid injection CVD, in which metal precursors are in a solution rather than in a solid form, was also used to grow textured polycrystalline Y_2O_3 films on Si (Figure 2a,b)³⁶. In contrast to ALD films, only the Y_2O_3 cubic phase was identified by XRD and PL spectroscopy, which can be explained by a higher deposition temperature (> 650 °C). Doping concentrations were first varied over a broad range, up to 100% in 200 nm thick films. As expected, since Eu^{3+} doping at high concentrations creates disorder in the crystal, Γ_{inh} shows an inverted bell-shape dependence as a function of Eu^{3+} concentration. The maximum value of 325 GHz is observed at 50% doping, while the lowest value of 50 GHz is observed for a 0.25% Eu^{3+} concentration. At similar concentrations, these values are smaller than those obtained by ALD, indicating a higher crystalline quality of the films. At 2% Eu^{3+} concentration and

TABLE 1 Optical properties of rare earth doped thin films. Structures are labeled by p (polycrystalline), e (epitaxial), and sc (single crystal). Transition wavelengths (λ), excited state population lifetimes (T_1), inhomogeneous (Γ_{inh}) and homogeneous (Γ_h) linewidths, as well as measurement temperatures are given. Γ_h was measured by SHB unless specified by pe (photon echo) or s (saturation). Values for bulk crystals are provided for comparison.

Crystal//substrate	Rare Earth conc.	Site sym.	Growth	Thickn. (nm)	λ (nm)	T_1 (ms)	Γ_{inh} (GHz)	Γ_h (MHz)	Temp. (K)	Refs.
Y ₂ O ₃ bulk	2% Eu ³⁺	C ₂	-	-	580.8	0.9	10	0.0008, pe	1.6	78
Y ₂ O ₃ //sapphire	2% Eu ³⁺	C ₂	CVD,p	3000	580.8	0.9	90	12	1.4	79
Y ₂ O ₃ //Si	5% Eu ³⁺	C ₂	ALD,p	100	580.88	0.7	200		10	45
Y ₂ O ₃ //Si	0.25-100% Eu ³⁺	C ₂	CVD,p	200	580.88	1	50-325	11 (a)	2	36
Y ₂ O ₃ //Si	2% Eu ³⁺	C ₂	CVD,p	80-2220	580.88		18-170	5-11.5	3	37
Y ₂ O ₃ //Gd ₂ O ₃ //Si	2% Eu ³⁺	C ₂	CVD,p	255	580.88		130	0.35	0.8	37
Y ₂ O ₃ bulk	50ppm Er ³⁺	C ₂	-	-	1535.6	8.5	0.780	0.005, pe (b)	3.5	80
Y ₂ O ₃ (222)//Si(111)	10-200ppm Er ³⁺	C ₂	MBE,e	400-1800	1535.6	8.1	5-37		4	46
CeO ₂ (111)//Si(111)	3-130ppm Er ³⁺	O _h	MBE,e	940	1530.74	2.7-4.5	10-42	0.44, pe 4.8-17, s	3.5	38,81
TiO ₂ bulk (rut.)	Er ³⁺	D _{2h}	-	-	1520.5	5.3	0.46		5	82
TiO ₂ (ana.)//Si	0.0035% Er ³⁺		MPE,p	25-75	1532.8	2	11.1-5.2		3.5	39
TiO ₂ (ana.)//SrTiO ₃	0.0035% Er ³⁺		MBE,e	25	1532.4	2	18.9		3.5	39
TiO ₂ (ana.)//LaAlO ₃	0.01-0.4% Er ³⁺	D _{2d}	MBE,e	18	1534		5.2-22.7		4.5	42
TiO ₂ (ana.)//Si	0.0017-4 % Er ³⁺		ALD,p	30	1532	0.7-1.7	60-100	235-560, s	3.5	83
Si//SOI	1ppm Er ³⁺		CVD,e	190	1536	0.142	0.4	0.009, s	8	44
Si//SOI	Er ³⁺		sc	220	1536	0.227	1.9	0.028, s (c)	2	53
LiNbO ₃ bulk	0.1% Tm ³⁺	C ₁ - C ₃	-	-	794	0.16	300	0.03, pe	1.7	2
LNOI	0.1% Tm ³⁺	C ₁ - C ₃	sc	300	794	0.157	330	0.225, pe	3.6	54,84
LiNbO ₃ bulk	50ppm Er ³⁺	C ₁ - C ₃	-	-	1532	2	180	0.004, pe (d)	1.6	2
LNOI	Er ³⁺	C ₁ - C ₃	sc	600	1532	3	170		3.6	56
LNOI	100ppm Er ³⁺	C ₁ - C ₃	sc	600	1532		166	0.0018, pe	0.02	34
LiNbO ₃ bulk	50ppm ¹⁷¹ Yb ³⁺	C ₁ - C ₃	-	-	980.5	0.44	50	0.035, pe	6	85
LNOI	¹⁷¹ Yb ³⁺	C ₁ - C ₃	sc	470	980.5	0.44	64	1-9 (e)	5	85,59

^a2% Eu³⁺ doping.

^bunder 0.5 T

^cunder 9 T, 9 MHz at zero-field

^dunder 0.5 T

^e48 MHz for for natural abundant Yb³⁺ ions

TABLE 2 Limiting factors and possible mitigations for optical inhomogeneous and homogeneous linewidths of rare earth doped thin films.

Platform	Limiting factors	Mitigations
All	RE proximity to surface	buffer/cap layers thicker films
	defects, impurities	non-polar site sym. epitaxy
	host spins	high mag. field & low temp. clock transitions magnetic field
Oxide films on Si	diffusion/oxidation at Si interface	buffer layers other substrates
Si	small bandgap host spins	- isotopic enrich.
LiNbO ₃	disorder host spins	- magnetic field

2 K, a homogeneous linewidth of $\Gamma_h=11$ MHz was measured by SHB in a 200 nm thick film, comparable to that obtained in the μ m thick films mentioned above, but still much broader than bulk values.

A subsequent study explored the usefulness of high-temperature annealing to improve inhomogeneous and homogeneous linewidths³⁷. Indeed, such treatments have proved very beneficial in Eu³⁺:Y₂O₃ nanoparticles. Applying them to thin films is, however, more complex. TEM and time-of-flight (TOF) SIMS analyses concluded that as-grown films deposited at 650 °C showed three well-defined parts: the Si substrate, a 10 nm SiO₂ layer grown prior to deposition, and the 100 nm thick Y₂O₃ film itself (Figure 2c). However, after post-annealing at 1100 and 1200 °C for 2 h, Si is oxidized by oxygen diffusion through the film, and the SiO₂ layer thickness increases. Moreover, because of Si and Y inter-diffusion, layers of mixed yttrium silicates form with a thickness reaching 900 nm at 1200 °C (Figure 2c). These results were confirmed by PL and PLE spectra in 2% Eu³⁺ films that showed new lines after annealing.

To avoid the effects of oxidation and inter-diffusion on RE ions, they were then doped in an 80 nm thick layer isolated from the Si/Y₂O₃ and Y₂O₃/air interfaces by 80 nm buffer and capping layers. This resulted in only moderate improvement upon annealing, which significantly increased Γ_{inh} from the as-grown value of 40 GHz in all cases. The multi-layered structures were, however, necessary to observe SHB. With increasing annealing temperature, a decrease of Γ_h was observed

FIGURE 5 Optical spectroscopy of rare earth doped thin films. (a) Left: XRD patterns of epitaxial (111) Y_2O_3 thin films deposited on (111)Si by MBE. A 400 nm thick Er^{3+} doped layer is sandwiched between buffer and cap layers of varying thicknesses. Right: inhomogeneous linewidths of Er^{3+} transition at 1535.6 nm recorded by PLE spectroscopy at 4 K. The narrowest line is obtained for thick cap and buffer layers. Adapted under the terms of the CC-BY license.⁴⁶ ©2020, M. Singh et al. (b) Photon echo decays of Er^{3+} at 1532 nm in a $LiNbO_3$ film obtained by top-down fabrication. Left: echo decay as a function of pulse separation at 20 mK and 0.4 T, giving $T_2 = 180 \mu s$ or $\Gamma_h = 1.8$ kHz. Right: T_2 and Γ_h dependences on magnetic field and temperature. Adapted with permission.³⁴ ©2022, American Physical Society. (c) Spectral hole recorded at 0.8 K at 581 nm in an epitaxial $Eu^{3+}:Y_2O_3$ CVD film deposited on an epitaxial Gd_2O_3 buffer deposited on Si by MBE. The corresponding homogeneous linewidth is 0.35 MHz. Adapted under the terms of the CC-BY license.⁸⁶ ©2025, D. Serrano et al. (d) Saturation spectroscopy (TSHB) of Er^{3+} ions implanted in a CVD Si film on Si at 3.5 K. A series of peaks equally spaced in frequency excite the PL in the saturation regime (left inset), resulting in a varying intensity as a function of the detuning between the peaks (right inset). This allows determining the homogeneous linewidth as a function of the excitation power (main plot) for Er^{3+} ions in two sites (in blue and red). The bottom dashed lines represent the radiative limits. Adapted under the terms of the CC-BY license.⁴⁴ ©2022, A. Gritsch et al.

from 11.5 to 9 MHz at 3 K. It showed a linear dependence on temperature with a slope of 0.5 MHz/K. Together with the works on $Er^{3+}:Y_2O_3$ films (see below), these results suggest that the Si- Y_2O_3 interface has a high concentration of defects that affect both Γ_{inh} and Γ_h likely through strain, electric noise, and TLS. This is confirmed by a 200 nm film with a $2 \mu m$ buffer and 20 nm cap which showed the narrowest linewidths: $\Gamma_{inh} = 18$ GHz and $\Gamma_h = 5$ MHz. A recent study showed that Γ_h can be decreased by more than an order of magnitude in a 255 nm thick Y_2O_3 CVD grown film deposited on a 222 nm epitaxial Gd_2O_3 film deposited on a Si substrate by MBE⁸⁶. This hybrid approach resulted in an epitaxial Y_2O_3 film with homogeneous linewidths down to 0.35 MHz at 800 mK (Figure 5c). This was attributed to a lowering of structural defects and absence of Si diffusion, although a large inhomogeneous linewidth of 130 GHz was observed.

Properties of 250 nm thick $Er^{3+}:Y_2O_3$ thin films deposited by CVD on various substrates were also reported⁴³. Strong texture and epitaxial growth were observed in the case of deposition on e.g. an epitaxial Y_2O_3/Si template and yttrium stabilized zirconia (YSZ), whereas inhomogeneous linewidths between 9 and 20 GHz were recorded for the

telecom wavelength transition ($^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{13/2}$ at 1536 nm) at a doping level of 700 ppm.

In a different approach, epitaxial films of (111) Y_2O_3 deposited on (111)Si substrates were obtained by MBE, taking advantage of the small lattice mismatch between the two crystalline structures (-2.4%)⁴⁶. Si oxidation and formation of yttrium silicates at the substrate/film interface were observed by TEM and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) with increasing temperature and growth time. This motivated a study of sandwiching a 50 ppm Er^{3+} doped Y_2O_3 layer (400 nm thickness) between two undoped ones. With a 100 and 200 nm buffer and cap layers respectively, the inhomogeneous linewidth at 1536 nm was reduced from 37.4 GHz for the bare film to 19.6 GHz (Figure 5a). Further studies showed a clear inverse correlation between the overall film thickness and Γ_{inh} . The lowest value of $\Gamma_{inh} = 5.1$ GHz was thus found in a 1.8 μm thick film with a 1 μm buffer. Importantly, no correlation between optical properties and crystalline quality as measured by XRD rocking curves or with Er concentration up to 200 ppm was found. Co-doping with lanthanum to adjust the lattice mismatch with Si did not decrease Γ_{inh} because the high concentration needed (17%) caused

significant disorder in the crystalline structure. As in the case of the polycrystalline films, it can be concluded that the Si/Y₂O₃ interface plays a critical role in inhomogeneous broadening. Moreover, despite thick buffers, Γ_{inh} remained large as compared to bulk materials that exhibit sub-GHz linewidth in this concentration range⁸⁹. This could be due to strain and defects caused by high-temperature growth followed by cool-down to the few K temperatures at which spectroscopic experiments are performed.

CeO₂ is a potentially good host for obtaining long optical and spin coherence lifetimes because it has a very low magnetic moment density as Ce⁴⁺ is non-paramagnetic and all naturally abundant isotopes have zero nuclear spins. Moreover, the Ce site has an O_h point group symmetry that prevents permanent electric dipole moments, which gives low sensitivity to electric noise, if doping ions, which are usually trivalent, occupy a site with this symmetry. Because of a favorable lattice mismatch of -0.4%, CeO₂(111) can be grown epitaxially on silicon (111) (Figure 2d) and has been investigated at 3.5 K with Er³⁺ doping concentrations between 3 and 130 ppm³⁸. For a 940 nm thick film, the transition at 1530.74 nm has an inhomogeneous linewidth of ≈ 10 up to 42 GHz when Er³⁺ concentrations increased. This could be due to the charge compensation needed to accommodate Er³⁺ ions in this crystal. The homogeneous linewidth, determined by saturation spectroscopy at zero magnetic field, follows the same trend and increases from 4.8 MHz to 1.5 GHz, which could also be related to charge compensation rather than Er³⁺-Er³⁺ interactions given their relatively low concentration. Post-annealing up to 900 °C was found to significantly improve Γ_{inh} down to 6.7 GHz and excited state T₁ up to 4.5 ms. It had, however, no positive effect on Γ_h . A further study by photon echoes of the same transition and under the same conditions suggests a homogeneous linewidth of $\Gamma_h = 1/(\pi \times 720) \text{ ns} = 440 \text{ kHz}$ ⁸¹. This 10-fold improvement over the previous measurement could be due to a large suppression of spectral diffusion at short times.

TiO₂ is another host crystal that shows reduced magnetic noise due to the low abundance of titanium isotopes with non-zero nuclear spins. Films of TiO₂ have been deposited on sapphire (r-plane orientation), (100) SrTiO₃ (STO), and (100) silicon with a 35 ppm Er³⁺ doping (Figure 2e)³⁹. On the silicon substrates, the films were polycrystalline with the anatase or rutile structures depending on the growth temperatures. The STO and sapphire substrates enabled epitaxial growth of the anatase and rutile phases, respectively. Interestingly, the 25 nm thick films (with a buffer-active layer-cap structure) showed a larger Γ_{inh} when epitaxially grown. This pointed to a low contribution to Γ_{inh} of the defects at grain boundaries in the polycrystalline films. A linewidth of 11.2 GHz was obtained for a TiO₂ film deposited on Si with the anatase phase. Increasing the buffer thickness to 60 nm resulted in $\Gamma_{inh} = 5.2 \text{ GHz}$, whereas increasing Er³⁺ concentration above 100 ppm led to a quick increase in linewidth, up to 1000 GHz at 0.4% doping level. This is likely to involve defects related to the charge compensation needed for introducing Er³⁺ ions in TiO₂.

Another substrate on which TiO₂ can grow epitaxially in the anatase structure is LaAlO₃, thanks to a small lattice mismatch of 0.3%. In films

of 18 nm thickness, Γ_{inh} decreased with decreasing Er³⁺ concentration down to 5.3 GHz below 100 ppm⁴². This value could be further improved by growing buffer and cap layers of about 10 nm. In these films, Er³⁺ crystal field levels are consistent with a substitution of Ti⁴⁺ but with a site symmetry of D_{2d} instead of C_{2v}, which can be assigned to charge compensation and/or site distortion.

TiO₂ films were also grown by ALD on silicon substrates at low temperature, resulting in amorphous structures⁸³. Post-annealing resulted in the crystallization of mostly the anatase phase while preserving the low roughness of the as-grown films, which can be useful for low-loss photonic structures. Films with 30 nm thickness (including 10 nm buffer and cap layers) showed linewidths between 60 and 100 GHz unrelated to Er³⁺ concentration between 1.7 and 40000 ppm. Measurements of Γ_h by saturation spectroscopy gave a value of $\Gamma_h = 235 \text{ MHz}$ at 1.7 ppm, suggesting large electric noise or TLS contributions.

In the examples shown above, RE-doped oxide thin films deposited on Si and other substrates show linewidths that tend to be significantly broader than those in bulk materials. Buffer and cap layers can mitigate these effects to some extent but also locate the ions further from interfaces, which may reduce coupling to external photonic structures. Inhomogeneous broadening could be limited by differences in thermal expansion coefficients during growth and/or processing at elevated temperatures and, therefore, difficult to decrease to very low values. It is, however, not a parameter as crucial as narrow homogeneous linewidths. The latter are so far broader than what could be expected from bulk crystals and need to be decreased to progress toward experiments such as quantum storage. A promising way is to use crystals in which RE ions sit in a high symmetry site, such as the C_{3i} site in Y₂O₃, to avoid electric noise⁹². In addition, TLS contribution could be reduced in films with lower concentration of structural defects and at ultra-low temperatures.

3.3 | Optical Properties of Rare Earth Implanted in Silicon Films

As mentioned above, silicon is a most mature platform for photonics, including the fabrication of integrated circuits for quantum applications. Similar to TiO₂ and CeO₂, it is moreover a material with a low concentration of nuclear spins, which can be furthermore grown with the $I = 0$ ²⁸Si isotope⁹³ and with very low levels of impurities and defects, which is attractive for long-lived quantum states.

A series of thin films with thicknesses between 0.2 and 2 μm were studied based on a SOI structure⁴⁴. This enabled creating mm long waveguides, which were needed to collect enough fluorescence for spectroscopic measurements. The films were obtained by Czochralski, floating zone, and CVD techniques. Prior to waveguide fabrication, erbium was implanted at low doses into the films with concentrations estimated between 1 and 0.1 ppm in the three main crystallographic sites. To avoid the formation of additional sites, the samples were annealed at low temperatures (500 °C). Inhomogeneous linewidths for the

prominent transitions in the 1535 - 1538 nm range were remarkably narrow, between 0.37 and 1 GHz depending on the site and growth method. Another unusual feature is the very short excited state lifetimes observed for two sites, $T_1 = 142$ and $183 \mu\text{s}$, which were considered of radiative origin. This can be partially explained by the high refractive index of silicon ($n = 3.48$). Homogeneous linewidths were measured in these sites by saturation spectroscopy at 9 kHz at low excitation power in all samples (**Figure 5d**), a marked improvement over films implanted with different conditions⁷⁰ and a value approaching those of Er^{3+} doped bulk oxide crystals. Γ_h values were unchanged between 1 and 8 K, a feature attributed to particularly large crystal field splittings for Er^{3+} in these sites and the high Debye temperature of Si.

Implantation in commercially fabricated waveguides was also investigated and showed broader inhomogeneous and homogeneous lines, up to 4 GHz and 9 MHz⁵³. At a high magnetic field of 9 T, Γ_h is considerably narrower and reached 28 kHz, as measured by saturation spectroscopy, thus approaching the best values previously reported⁴⁴. This also suggests that additional impurities carrying electron spins are present in these samples.

These thin film results compare well to those recently obtained in implanted bulk Si⁹⁴. Using higher Er^{3+} doses and O co-implantation, 70 sites were detected, with inhomogeneous and homogeneous linewidths down to 0.4 GHz and 0.75 MHz respectively at 300 mK. Excited state lifetimes ranged from 0.5 to 1.5 ms.

Si is an attractive platform with a transparency window compatible with Er^{3+} telecom wavelength transition at $1.5 \mu\text{m}$, but not with other RE ions investigated for QT like Yb^{3+} or Eu^{3+} . For Er^{3+} in specific sites, the inhomogeneous and homogeneous linewidths are narrow, already close to those observed in some bulk oxide crystals, and the transitions particularly strong. Γ_h could be further improved by material engineering to reduce electric and magnetic noise from defects and impurities. It could also be possible to obtain higher concentrations of Er^{3+} in the desired sites, to increase absorption for quantum memories or enable quantum gates between nearby ions.

3.4 | Optical Properties of Rare Earth in Doped/Implanted Lithium Niobate Films

LiNbO_3 is another platform for high-quality optoelectronic structures that can be easily doped with RE ions. In bulk crystals, long optical coherence lifetimes were observed for several RE ions despite Nb and Li having both 100% abundant non-zero nuclear spin isotopes^{95,96,85}.

LNOI films (**Figure 3**) of 300 nm in thickness were obtained from a 0.1 % Tm^{3+} doped bulk crystal and processed to create waveguides⁵⁴. At 3.6 K, the ${}^3\text{H}_6 \rightarrow {}^3\text{H}_4$ transition at 794 nm had an inhomogeneous linewidth of about 300 GHz, similar to the initial bulk crystal. This large value is due to the disorder related to non-stoichiometry and charge compensation in LiNbO_3 . SHB was performed with these samples and gave a homogeneous linewidth of 800 kHz. This value was limited by spectral diffusion as shown by later photon echo measurements, which gave $\Gamma_h = 225$ kHz, comparable to that of bulk crystals⁸⁴.

Similar LNOI structures, with films 600 nm thick, were implanted with Er^{3+} ions located at 80 nm below the film surface and annealed at 550°C to repair implantation damage⁵⁶. Prior to implantation, waveguides and ring resonators were etched and a 30 nm layer of SiO_2 was deposited on the surface by CVD. At 2.6 K, the transition at 1532 nm has a broadening $\Gamma_{\text{inh}} = 170$ GHz, identical to the bulk value. To avoid potential damages caused by implantation and subsequent annealing, a further study used 100 ppm Er^{3+} doped crystals to fabricate LNOI and then resonators and waveguides³⁴. A linewidth of $\Gamma_{\text{inh}} = 166$ GHz was measured in these structures, similar to values in the bulk crystal. At 20 mK and under a magnetic field of 0.55 T to mitigate spectral diffusion from non-excited Er^{3+} ions, coherent lifetimes of $180 \mu\text{s}$ ($\Gamma_h = 1.8$ kHz) were measured by photon echoes, also close to the expected bulk values (**Figure 5b**).

LNOI films containing ytterbium, which ${}^2\text{F}_{7/2} \rightarrow {}^2\text{F}_{5/2}$ transition lies in the near-infrared around 980 nm, were also investigated⁵⁹. The 470 nm thick films were implanted and annealed at 650°C and etched to create waveguides and resonators. A Yb^{3+} inhomogeneous linewidth of 64 GHz was observed as well as a 48 MHz homogeneous linewidth, determined by SHB at 3.5 K. The latter value was comparable to the 29 MHz linewidth recorded on a 100 ppm doped bulk crystal and the 42 MHz one found in the LNOI film before structuring. Further improvement in homogeneous linewidth was obtained by implanting ${}^{171}\text{Yb}^{3+}$ in which optical and spin transitions are insensitive to magnetic field fluctuations around $B = 0$ at first order, a property known as clock or zero first order Zeeman transitions⁹⁷. Here, at 5 K and an estimated Yb^{3+} concentration of 3 ppm, Γ_h reduces to 9 MHz, with an even narrower component of 1 MHz. A 50 ppm doped bulk crystal gave a comparable value of $\Gamma_h = 3$ MHz by SHB whereas PE measurements gave $\Gamma_h = 35$ kHz⁸⁵.

Films obtained from RE-doped LiNbO_3 crystals show the narrowest homogeneous linewidths reported so far in thin films. They are identical to those of bulk crystals, showing that the fabrication process produces few defects, at least far from surfaces. Moreover, results on ${}^{171}\text{Yb}^{3+}$ suggest that implantation and post-annealing methods could be developed to reach the same results. An intrinsic limitation of LiNbO_3 is, however, its partially disordered structure that leads to broad RE inhomogeneous linewidths, up to 1500 GHz for Pr^{3+} ⁹⁵, and a large nuclear spin bath, especially significant for paramagnetic RE ions.

3.5 | Spin Properties of Rare Earth in Thin Films

Most studies on ensembles of ions in thin films for QT focus on optical properties and spin ones have been reported only in a few cases.

Spin coherence and relaxation times in 3 ppm Er^{3+} doped CeO_2 films with a 940 nm thickness were studied by EPR in the X band⁸¹. Field-swept echo measurements at 3.6 K gave $g = 6.8$ and a spin inhomogeneous broadening of 245 MHz at a magnetic field of 0.1 T. This linewidth is about one order of magnitude broader compared to bulk crystals such as YSO^{98,99} and is attributed to defects and strain in the film. The spin coherence lifetime, measured by Hahn echoes, was

$T_2 = 0.25 \mu\text{s}$. This could be due to Er^{3+} instantaneous diffusion, which reduces with Er^{3+} concentration, to interaction with paramagnetic impurities, such as Ce^{3+} ions, and to TLS related to residual disorder. Spin-lattice relaxation times had a long component of about 1 ms, which was confirmed by an optical pump-probe method, and a shorter one of 0.1 ms.

In $^{171}\text{Yb}^{3+}$ implanted waveguides fabricated in LNOI films, optically detected magnetic resonance was used to determine inhomogeneous linewidths of about 100 MHz at 5 K and zero magnetic field⁸⁵. A spectral hole was burned in the spin transition, corresponding to a homogeneous linewidth of 5 MHz, which was surprisingly narrower than the one obtained in a bulk crystal, possibly due to a higher $^{171}\text{Yb}^{3+}$ concentration in the latter.

Recently a single Er^{3+} spin in a Si thin film was optically detected and its properties investigated. These results are reported in Section 4.2.

4 | OPTICAL QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES WITH THIN FILMS

4.1 | Quantum Memories

Quantum memories (QM) that can store and release on-demand photonic qubits such as single photons find applications in long-distance quantum communications, as parts of quantum repeaters, and quantum computing^{101,102}. They can keep quantum information carried by light localized for long times, which enables synchronizing photons in optical quantum computers and quantum networks, leading to more efficient gate operations and entanglement distribution over distant nodes.

These so-called absorptive memories can be implemented with ensembles of optical centers, a situation well suited to RE-doped materials since high doping concentrations can be obtained. QM have been investigated in bulk crystals for many years, and this topic is arguably the most advanced in RE-based QT at the moment¹⁴. Waveguides made of thin films can strongly confine light and offer the advantage of using less optical power for the control pulses used to store and retrieve photonic qubits, which decreases noise added to the released photons. They can also enable higher absorption and thus improved memory efficiency because long optical paths can be exploited. This is an important point for RE ions weak transitions. Moreover, in the case of paramagnetic ions like Er^{3+} and Yb^{3+} , concentrations below ≈ 50 ppm may have to be used in QM protocols requiring efficient optical pumping¹⁰. Using QM for quantum communications or computing also requires multiple additional components, like single photon sources, beam splitters, and detectors, that could ultimately benefit from on-chip integration.

A QM protocol has been investigated in an LNOI thin film made out of a 0.1 % doped Tm^{3+} bulk crystal⁸⁴. Named the Atomic Frequency Comb (AFC), it is based on the rephasing, at a specific time, of photons absorbed in a series of regularly spaced spectral peaks. As such, it is a fixed delay memory but can be converted to an on-demand one with the addition of optical pulses, to transfer coherence to a spin transition,

or of electric field pulses^{103,104}. It enables low-noise operation, as well as efficient multiplexed storage in the spectral/temporal domain, which is a key resource to achieve high entanglement rate distribution for cascaded quantum repeaters. The AFC protocol has been implemented in many crystals^{105,106,107} and used to demonstrate, for example, remote entanglement between separate crystals¹⁴. The sub-wavelength size waveguides that can be created in LNOI films can reach very low losses and are thus attractive for high-efficiency QM.

Single-mode ridge waveguides of $176 \times 400 \text{ nm}^2$ were etched in the LNOI films, allowing for strong light confinement over a length of 1 mm. This results in a high Rabi frequency of 45 MHz for $1 \mu\text{W}$ of power in the waveguide, a three-order of magnitude improvement over waveguides in bulk crystals with larger cross-sections¹⁹. The AFC spectral profile was created by optical pumping at 794 nm ($^3\text{H}_6 \rightarrow ^3\text{H}_4$ transition) with the metastable $^3\text{F}_4$ electronic level as a shelving state. In this way, a 100 MHz wide structure was created with variable separation between the spectral teeth, corresponding to storage times between 90 and 250 ns (Figure 6a). The maximum storage time is fixed by the coherence lifetime of the transition, $1.4 \mu\text{s}$ ($\Gamma_h = 225 \text{ kHz}$). At the shortest storage time, the memory efficiency was 0.14 %. This value could be improved by creating narrower peaks with optimized optical pumping techniques, in the limit of the spectral diffusion linewidth, and increasing the optical depth in longer and low-loss waveguides.

Another approach is to fabricate structures in LNOI and subsequently implant them with RE ions. Ridge waveguides and ring resonators of $300 \mu\text{m}$ diameter were etched in a 600 nm thick LNOI film¹⁰⁸. These structures had an 800 nm width, resulting in strong mode confinement. Implantation of Yb^{3+} ions at moderate doses of 10^{12} ions/ cm^2 resulted in a peak concentration of about 2 ppm. These low doses reduce implantation damages and magnetic ion-ion interactions as Yb^{3+} is paramagnetic. After annealing, the losses in waveguides and resonators due to implantation damages are reduced, and quality factors for the latter can reach 2.8×10^6 off-resonance. Such structures could be used to design critically coupled, also known as impedance-matched, resonators in which the incoming photons are totally absorbed by the resonant ions¹⁰⁹. The memory efficiency can thus achieve up to unit efficiency, assuming negligible additional losses in the resonators.

Similar designs were investigated with Er^{3+} ions⁵⁶. Here, the ring resonators had a smaller diameter of $70 \mu\text{m}$ and an average Q factor of 500k after implantation and annealing. Er^{3+} properties were investigated in a device with $Q = 200\text{k}$, showing a Purcell factor of 3.8 for the coherent transition at 1532 nm. This corresponded to a decrease in the fluorescence lifetime from 3.2 to 0.618 ms. As mentioned in Section 3.4, in an approach where structures were created in a film obtained from a doped crystal³⁴, photon echoes were used to measure an Er^{3+} coherence lifetimes of $180 \mu\text{s}$ at 1532 nm. This gives a long upper limit for storage in the optical transition and could furthermore enable using transfer pulses for extended storage in spin transitions. This would be facilitated by the high Rabi frequency that can be achieved in waveguides with strong mode confinement.

FIGURE 6 Towards applications in quantum technologies. (a) Coherent optical storage in a Tm^{3+} :LNOI waveguide at 3.6 K. An input pulse resonant with an atomic frequency comb (AFC) created by SHB in Tm^{3+} inhomogeneously broadened transition is sent to the sample at $t = 0$. A fraction of the pulse is stored in the memory and re-emitted after a delay between 90 and 250 ns, which is determined by the AFC structure. Adapted with permission.⁸⁴ ©2023, American Chemical Society. (b) Left: an Yb^{3+} LNOI thin film with embedded waveguide, resonator, and top and bottom electrodes. Right: an applied voltage can tune the resonator off- and on-resonance with Yb^{3+} transition, modulating the Purcell enhancement and PL decay (blue and orange curves respectively). At 8 K, this enables fast control of Yb^{3+} spontaneous emission. Adapted with permission.⁵⁹ ©2022, Optica Publishing Group. (c) Single Er^{3+} detection in a TiO_2 film deposited on Si and coupled to a nanophotonic resonator at 3.4 K. Left: the resonator provides a strong Purcell enhancement as evidenced by the 460 fold shortening of the excited state decay time (in purple) compared to ions outside the resonator (in grey). Right: autocorrelation measurement of a single ion with a zero delay corrected value of $g^2(0) = 0.04$. Adapted with permission.¹⁰⁰ ©2024, AIP Publishing. (d) PLE spectrum of Er^{3+} ions in a nanophotonic resonator fabricated in an implanted CVD Si film on Si at 14 K. At short delays after excitation, lines corresponding to single ions in the resonator (e.g. denoted by the black arrow) are observed. For longer integration times, signals from background ions in feeding waveguides are recorded (grey line). Adapted with permission.⁵⁸ ©2023, Optica Publishing Group.

Silicon films containing Er^{3+} can also show good properties for QM. As for LNOI, moderate implantation doses, on the order of 10^{12} ions/ cm^2 were used to limit implantation damages and ion-ion interactions⁴⁴. An additional concern is the formation at high doses and high annealing temperatures of Er^{3+} centers with unfavorable properties at the expense of those with good ones. Multiple implantation energies and doses were used to achieve uniform doping across the films, hence optimal overlap with the light mode in guiding structures. In 200 nm thick and 700 nm wide waveguides fabricated after implantation and post-annealed, strong light confinement was expected. However, losses were found to increase from 3.5 dB to 6 dB/cm after implantation. Low-loss (1.5 dB/cm) commercial waveguides were also investigated with similar implantation and annealing procedures, which seems to preserve low losses in cm-long waveguides⁵³. Er^{3+} homogeneous linewidths can reach 28 kHz at high magnetic field and low power (Section 3.3), setting an upper limit for optical storage time of about 10 μs and opening the possibility of transfer to spin states for longer storage time.

Further improvements for thin film-based quantum memories should first include increasing optical coherence times, especially for bottom-up grown films. This is useful for pure optical storage but, more importantly, to implement coherence transfer to spin states. Indeed, this is required to achieve the tens of ms to 1 s storage times needed for practical applications¹⁰⁶. In this respect, μs range optical T_2 may be sufficient given the high Rabi frequency achievable in nanoscale waveguides. This scheme assumes long spin coherence times, which remains to be demonstrated. It should also be noted that alternative QM protocols have been proposed in which heavy frequency multiplexing compensates for relatively short storage times and thus does not need spin transitions^{110,111}. The second parameter that is crucial to improve is QM efficiency, which is decreased by fiber-to-chip coupling and propagation losses in the structures. Absorption within the storage bandwidth should also be as high as possible, which may require lower inhomogeneous linewidths, although the possibility of using long waveguides or impedance-matched resonators can mitigate this requirement.

4.2 | Single Rare Earth Ion Based Devices

Single RE ions are investigated as single photon sources and qubits for applications in quantum communications and processing^{22,21}. Of particular interest in the first case is the possibility of exploiting RE optical and spin degrees of freedom to create long-lived spin-photon entanglement. However, the entanglement of remote spins also requires indistinguishable emitted photons and should be carried out at high rates. The first condition can be matched since RE ions can show small long-term spectral diffusion and their transitions can be tuned by electric or magnetic fields¹¹². As RE ions are dim emitters, the second requirement demands a strong enhancement of their spontaneous emission rate, which can be obtained through the Purcell effect in high-Q and small mode volume resonators. One additional attractive feature of RE ions is the availability of transitions with high quantum yield in the infrared, in particular with Er^{3+} and Yb^{3+} at 1.5 and 0.98 μm . Lifetime-limited emissions^{21,55} have been reported in several systems, as well as the emission of indistinguishable photons at 1.5 μm for Er^{3+} ions in a bulk crystal coupled to a surface resonator²⁹.

Single RE spins are also investigated for quantum processing^{28,27}. An attractive scheme is to use optical transitions for readout and control of individual long-lived spin qubits in dense ensembles²⁰. Given that inhomogeneous to homogeneous linewidth ratios can reach 10^5 or more¹, this approach enables selective addressing through optical frequencies, avoiding for example large numbers of electric connections or issues with selective microwave excitation. Two-qubit gates can also be implemented using electric dipole-dipole interactions in the optical excited state¹¹³, which prevents modifying the state of the qubits not involved in the gate. Finally, the optical transitions are ideally suited for distributing quantum states across remote RE processors to create quantum networks. As for single photon sources, strong Purcell enhancement is required for spin readout. This has been demonstrated with RE coupled to resonators milled in or deposited/patterned on top of bulk crystals^{26,29}.

Regarding quantum memories, thin film architectures would enable on-chip integration with other components such as interferometers and detectors and importantly could provide increased scalability in terms of qubits.

Single detection of implanted Yb^{3+} ions was reported in LNOI thin films in which micro-disk resonators were etched after implantation⁵⁹. A particular interest of LiNbO_3 in this context is its large electro-optic coefficient. Indeed, sandwiching between electrodes gave the resonators a tunability of 160 GHz, well above Yb^{3+} inhomogeneous linewidth $\Gamma_{\text{inh}} = 64$ GHz. This is useful to selectively address target ions or, within a given ion, transitions involving different spin levels. The resonators had a radius of 7 μm and Q-factors between 5×10^4 and 15×10^4 , allowing a 10-fold Purcell enhancement of Yb^{3+} emission, decreasing its lifetime from 430 to 38 μs at 8 K. As the resonator could be tuned on- and off-resonance in 5 μs , the spontaneous emission decay could be temporally shaped, a useful feature for single photon sources

(Figure 6b)⁶⁴. Single ion detection was achieved by tuning the resonators far away from the Yb^{3+} line center where the spectral density of ions is too large. With a 140 GHz detuning, discrete and stable peaks were detected in PLE spectra and attributed to single ions. The corresponding count rates were also consistent with this analysis but too low to perform second-order correlation experiments. The peak linewidth was 250 MHz broad, about 3 times larger than the Γ_h value deduced from SHB, presumably due to spectral diffusion on longer detection times. It was nevertheless small on timescales of several minutes.

An LNOI thin film fabricated from a 100 ppm doped bulk crystal was also used for single Er^{3+} detection¹¹⁴. The resonators were obtained by creating 1D nanobeam photonic crystal structures from a 300 nm thick film which was furthermore suspended by removing the underlying buffer SiO_2 . This resulted in a Q-factor of 10^5 to 1.6×10^5 and a mode volume of 0.55 μm^3 ($1.6(\lambda/n)^3$), and, for resonant Er^{3+} ions, in a decrease in excited state lifetime from 2.5 ms to 14 μs , i.e. a Purcell factor of 177 at 1 K. Thanks to electrodes placed on the sides of the resonator, the cavity could be tuned across 1.5 nm. Selecting an appropriate cavity allowed detecting isolated peaks about 2 nm away (255 GHz) from the line center which was $\Gamma_{\text{inh}} = 160$ GHz broad. A second-order autocorrelation measurement on an isolated peak gave $g^{(2)}(0) = 0.38$. This value is below the limit of 0.5 for a single emitter and a further analysis suggested that 80% of the photons were emitted by a single ion. The μs switching capability of the cavity was demonstrated on a single ion for which emission could be suppressed just after excitation by setting the cavity off-resonance. After 100 μs it was tuned back to resonance and the emission was retrieved. Single ion linewidths of tens of MHz were observed but could reach much narrower values, on the order of a few kHz, as shown by PE experiments at lower temperatures and under magnetic field in waveguide structures.

Single Er^{3+} detection was also achieved in TiO_2 thin films grown on a SOI wafer by MBE¹⁰⁰. TiO_2 anatase phase was chosen for a smoother surface as compared to the rutile phase, an important parameter for high-quality nanophotonic structures. An active layer of only 1 nm was placed between 15 nm buffer and capping layers for improved properties as discussed in Section 3.2. A 1D nanobeam photonic crystal cavity was then patterned on the silicon part of the structure, leading to a mode volume of $0.4(\lambda/n)^3$ and Q-factor of 4×10^4 . At 3.4 K, PLE spectra revealed discrete lines as the cavity resonance was tuned across the inhomogeneous linewidth by condensing gas on the structure. In this case, the number of ions in the mode volume was sufficiently small to see isolated peaks close to the line center frequency. Resonant ions showed a strong decrease in excited state lifetime, from 1.1 ms to 2.4 μs corresponding to a Purcell enhancement of 460 (Figure 6c). Single ion emission was confirmed by autocorrelation measurements leading to a dark-count corrected value of $g^{(2)}(0) = 0.04$ (Figure 6c). Single ion linewidths of 174 MHz were observed over the measurement time scale of several minutes, a value which slightly increased to a 209 MHz value when averaged over several hours. The latter highlights the long-term stability of Er^{3+} transition in these films.

Another approach to single Er^{3+} ions detection is to directly implant them in Si. A first series of works used optical excitation combined with electrical detection within a nano-transistor structure¹¹⁵. The latter enables single-electron charge sensing and thus single ion detection when Er^{3+} excited state relaxes non-radiatively towards a nearby electron trap, causing ionization of the latter. This method enabled in-depth spectroscopy of single Er^{3+} ions^{116,117} and individual Er^{3+} pairs¹¹⁸. Single ion linewidths down to 30 MHz were measured in these devices, possibly limited by charge fluctuations¹¹⁷.

Other works used optical detection, taking advantage of the very good properties of Er^{3+} ions in the specific crystallographic sites discussed in Section 3.3. Here, 1D nanobeam photonic crystals were fabricated in CVD Si films deposited on a SOI structure resulting in a mode volume of $1.45(\lambda/n)^3$ and Q-factor of 7×10^4 ⁵⁸. By selecting and tuning by gas condensation a cavity close to the line center, single peaks located about 1 GHz from line center ($\Gamma_{\text{inh}} = 0.5$ GHz) were detected at short times after excitation and low temperature (Figure 6d). This was necessary to reduce the background due to ions excited off-resonance or located in the waveguides feeding the resonators. An isolated line had a linewidth of 80 MHz, much broader than the 10 kHz homogeneous linewidth determined on ensembles of ions in waveguides. The emission decay time was $3.1 \mu\text{s}$ corresponding to a Purcell factor of 60, as the bulk lifetime is only $186 \mu\text{s}$. Under a small magnetic field, the line was narrow enough to split into two components, corresponding to the Zeeman levels of the ground and excited states. The single ion nature of the observed line was further confirmed by the observation of Rabi oscillations and autocorrelation measurements. The latter gave a corrected value of $g^2(0) = 0.39$, limited by background ions. In an optimized device with lower Er^{3+} concentration, a much lower value of $g^2(0) = 0.017$, at the detector dark counts level, was obtained.

A further study extended these results to Er^{3+} electron spins¹¹⁹. After Er^{3+} implantation into a commercial SOI film, an improved nanobeam cavity ($V = 0.83(\lambda/n)^3$, $Q = 8 \times 10^4$) led to a Purcell factor of 177, which resulted in a very short optical lifetime of $0.8 \mu\text{s}$ and a low $g^{(2)} = 0.02$ factor for a single ion resonant with the cavity. Applying a magnetic field of 0.3 T gave splittings larger than the optical transition linewidth for the ground and excited state spin levels. This allowed separately addressing spin-preserving and spin-flip transitions and performing spin initialization, state read-out, and measurement of a spin relaxation time of 0.44 s. Using additional microwave excitation, a ground state spin coherence lifetime of $48 \mu\text{s}$ was also determined by a spin echo experiment. This value is likely limited by magnetic noise due to paramagnetic impurities. Single-shot readout was next demonstrated by setting only one spin-preserving transition in resonance with the cavity. In general, due to limited detection efficiency, multiple excitation of the transition has to be performed to detect enough photons to confirm the spin state. This has to happen before the spin flips, which sets an upper limit on the number of excitation cycles (the cyclicity) that can be used for detection without re-initializing the spin state. In this system, a cyclicity of about 100 was measured, which resulted in a single-shot

readout fidelity of 87%. This could be improved with a better cavity and photon out-coupling.

The development of RE-doped thin films for single-ion-based applications is highly demanding in terms of materials and devices. The general considerations on optical and spin coherence discussed in Section 3 are especially relevant here. In particular, the resonators required for useful single photon sources typically have a small mode volume for strong Purcell enhancement and high emission rate. This locates RE ions close to surfaces which may increase decoherence and spectral diffusion through charge noise. In this case, systems that offer symmetry-protected sites for RE ions may be advantageous. Background signals may also be more significant when dealing with single ions. Although doped films, especially those made out of single crystals, typically offer better properties, localized implantation may ultimately be necessary with the added difficulty of repairing implantation damages without affecting resonators.

4.3 | Hybrid Systems

Thin film structures are attractive for creating hybrid systems combining different materials that can interact at their interface and offer new functionalities. In the field of nanoscale optoelectronics, Er^{3+} ions in close proximity to a graphene layer could have their emission turned on and off by varying a gate voltage¹²⁰. The structure was made of a silicon substrate on which a 60 nm thick Er^{3+} doped film was deposited by spin-coating. A graphene sheet was then placed on top of the oxide film before being covered by a transparent polymer gate. By varying the voltage between the top gate and the silicon substrate, the graphene Fermi energy E_F can be tuned. With Er^{3+} infrared emission at $1.5 \mu\text{m}$, i.e. an energy $E_m = 0.8$ eV, a regime where $E_F > 0.7E_m$ can be reached. This condition and the near field interaction enabled by the sub-wavelength $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ film, resulted in the demonstration of localized plasmons generation in the graphene layer after Er^{3+} excitation. Moreover, varying the gate voltage led to the electric control of Er^{3+} relaxation, from the creation of electron-hole pairs in the graphene layer to radiative emission and, finally, plasmon generation. Further work with improved devices and in particular a thinner ALD Er^{3+} YO film of 12 nm to increase interactions, showed that Er^{3+} emission could be electrically modulated at high speed up to μs time scales, much shorter than the Er^{3+} bare emission lifetime of 6 ms¹²¹. The modulation is provided by switching between the electron-hole pair and plasmon creation regimes. These results open prospects for quantum optoelectronic nanotechnologies where photon and plasmon waveforms can be controlled.

Thin film architectures made of an oxide film deposited on diamond were also investigated with the goal of creating new optically addressable spin systems¹²². In this approach, shallow NV^- color centers in a high-purity diamond CVD film can interact with Er^{3+} ions in a Y_2O_3 thin film grown on top of the diamond. This ensures that both quantum centers are located in high-quality environments that preserve their optical and spin quantum properties, while strong magnetic dipole-dipole

interactions are possible at the interface. In this way, the outstanding spin properties of the NV^- center¹²³ could be complemented with the Er^{3+} optical transition in the telecom range, opening the way to improved quantum communications and distributed computing or sensing. Growth of textured polycrystalline Y_2O_3 films by CVD was obtained with high crystalline quality in a broad range of deposition temperatures, as evidenced by structural studies and Er^{3+} PL spectroscopy. At 10 K, the latter showed well-resolved PL spectra at $1.5 \mu m$, and PL decays identical to those measured on bulk materials, thus confirming that Er^{3+} PL properties are preserved in the deposited thin films. Optical and spin properties of NV^- centers implanted at 4.5 and 8 nm were also studied before and after deposition of Y_2O_3 thin film. Despite the high growth temperature of $850^\circ C$ under oxygen atmosphere, no degradation of the diamond surface through oxidation was noticed. Moreover, the PL and optically detected magnetic resonance spectra were similar after Y_2O_3 deposition, showing that NV^- spin linewidths and populations lifetimes, as well as charge state were preserved. These results are first steps towards demonstrating $Er^{3+} - NV^-$ interactions in oxide-diamond thin film structures.

5 | CONCLUSION

RE-doped crystals are promising systems for optical QT as shown by numerous experiments on bulk crystals showing narrow homogeneous and inhomogeneous linewidths for optical and spin transitions. Moreover, these unique properties have been utilized in a number of breakthrough demonstrations, opening the way to applications in quantum communications and processing. Thin film-based architectures could advance these results further by enabling the integration of RE ions in on-chip photonic circuits and thus provide compact, stable, and scalable platforms for quantum photonics with functionalities such as quantum memories, single photon sources for spin-photon entanglement, and quantum processing.

Different platforms are currently investigated with distinctive advantages and challenges. The most flexible ones in terms of doping, composition, and multi-layer structures are those based on grown films on Si and other substrates. They, however, suffer so far from broad optical inhomogeneous and homogeneous linewidths, likely induced by defects, fluctuating electric fields, and perturbations by TLS. This could be improved by further developments in film growth and decoupling of RE from electric noise in high-symmetry crystallographic sites.

LNiO is another promising material that benefits from mature fabrication techniques for nanophotonics and from the good properties of RE ions in single-crystalline $LiNbO_3$. This is especially true when a doped crystal is used prior to thin film fabrication, which allows preserving bulk properties. In addition, $LiNbO_3$ is an electro-optic material that enables photon waveform shaping by tuning resonators on and off-resonance with RE transitions in short times.

Finally, Si can be implanted with Er^{3+} ions under specific conditions to lead to optical properties approaching those of bulk oxide

single crystals. Combined with the impressive quality of integrated SOI nano-photonics, these properties make Si a very attractive platform for exploiting RE quantum properties. It is, however, restricted to RE emitting in the infrared region, like Er^{3+} , and does not allow using the excellent spin properties of Eu^{3+} ions, for example.

Experiments opening the way to applications in QT have been reported in these three platforms. Coherent light storage or single ion detection have, for example, been demonstrated in various ion/crystal systems, taking advantage of the new possibilities offered by thin films, such as long waveguides with strong confinement or high-Q and small mode volume resonators. Another promising approach enabled by thin films is the creation of hybrid structures that could combine the properties of RE ions and other quantum centers. As a whole, these results, and the ongoing effort in material development, pave the way to advanced devices allowing, e.g. single photon quantum storage, highly coherent spin transitions, remote entanglement, or quantum gates.

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None reported.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no potential conflict of interest.

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